

Importance of Human Resource in Development of Indian Educational System

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Abstract

This research paper describes about Role of human resource Management in Educational institution. Educational Sector is plays vital role in Indian social and economic growth. For the advancement in any educational institution well educated, skilled and developed human resource is required. Human Resource Management (HRM) is use for recruitment, training, and welfare of Human Resource. Retention of good academic staff is very much important in development of institution.

In this paper we discuss about the function & Role of HRM and importance of Human Resource Management in sustainable growth of Educational Institute.

Introduction

Education is basic need of human been to live in society. Good institute is built by good academic staff as here stakeholder i.e student is directly in the contact with teacher who is the back bone of educational institution. The institute who is maintaining quality of teacher by providing different technical, nontechnical, ethical training to their staff member is always at top position. Result of Educational institute is measure by different factors like Result of student, Placement of student, Extra-curricular activities of students. This result can be achieved by good academic and supporting staff. Which is to be hire and trained by Human Resource Manager of Institution.

In this paper we will discuss about Role of Human Resource Management in Development of Indian education system. We will also discuss about organizational structure, rules of recruitment, different training that should be provided to academic staff for sustainable growth of Educational institution.

Objective of Research

Objective of research is to boost the Education system by changing the Human Behavior through enhanced Human Resource Policy.

As we discuss earlier education is a service industry so manpower is the biggest investment of the institution so human resource management have to work on improvement of the employee behavior, employee ethics and communication. So to manage and develop strong and sustainable human resource in proper way Human Resource Management (HRM) should perform various activities.

In this research we will study different human resource management HRM policies to increase the employee quality, employee satisfactions level, employee interiority. So result of all these should be reflecting in the quality of education, result and increases reputation of institution.

Role of HRM in Education

The major functions of HRM in educational institute are Staff Recruitment, staff relation, Staff Development, job appraisals. The institute whose human resource department who is doing all these works efficiently and ethically that institute is always performs well and is always at top position.

Staff Recruitment

The major function of Human Resource Department is staff procurement, Educational institution needs two type of human resource and they are Academic staff and supporting staff. Academic staff is back bone of institution as this staff is in direct contact with stakeholders (i.e. students, parents and alumni).

Recruitment is the first step of employment. It is the method by means of which employees are brought into industry. It is a Mechanism of finding suitable employees and encourage them for apply for a job in an organization. Recruitment involves listing of a number of candidates for any job so as to select the best person from among number of applicants. Recruitment is a positive function. Recruitment can be defined as an activity that brings the job applicants and employers face to face with one another to achieve certain goals.

Recruitment process should be transparent and ethical. In educational sector candidate must be well qualified, decent and must have command on language. In higher educational institute there are three designations of academic staff and they are Assistant Professor, Associate Professor, and Professor.

Different positions in higher educational institutes are registrar, accountant, assistant, clerk, attendant etc.

Staff Relation

Maintaining a good and healthy environment at work place is an important task of Human resource department. This healthy environment can be maintained by arranging different events, games, motivational talk for faculties and supporting staff. This also can be achieved by providing job appraisal, work rewards. Due to all this activities filling of belonging ness is develop among staff member that will directly impact on quality of work.

Staff Development

Staff development is very much important task of Human Resource Management HRM, to develop staff members in all aspect training is must. So HRM should provide training on Communication, Aptitude, moral ethics Etc.

Management should motivate academic staff for paper presentation, different workshop, Subject detailing workshop etc and should provide financial assistant to their staff so that quality of their Faculty will improve which will directly impacts on institute growth.

Job Appraisals

Every staff members should get appraisal according to his or her performance. Appraisal can be in the form of rewards, Salary hike, appreciation letter etc. Due to this positive and healthy environment is created among in working place.

Employee should get increment according to last one year performance only and it should be variable depending on his or her performance.

Organizational Structure of Educational Institute

Organizational structure of employee is an authority structure whose authority is decreases from top to bottom. Human Resource Management has to design good organizational structure of Institute and distribute authority according to the designation of staff member.

Generally chairman is at the top of authority chart, and authority decreases as vice chairman, Managing Director, Principal, HOD, Professor, Associate Professor, Assistant Professor, Lab assistant, Attendant etc. So HRM is work hard to maintain the dignity of every designation and maintaining the authority level.

Staff Retention as a factor of Growth

Any educational institute is known by its academic staff. The institute having good staff retention policy (i.e having old staff) is always growing institute. Now a days in Indian educational sector of higher Educational scenario is drastically changing, as government have change student to staff ratio so due to this decision of government many academic staff have lost their jobs or left the teaching field.

Due to this scenario it is very difficult for human resource management (HRM) to retain teaching and supporting staff. To retain good academic staff management should provide healthy wedges as per rule of AICTE or UGC which are the monitoring committees of higher educational Institute. So HRM should provide healthy working environment, proper increments according to performance of teacher. Performance of teacher should be measure fairly through results, feedback of students and R & D work done by the Staff.

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